

KWARA STATE UNIVERSITY, MALETE, NIGERIA

The University for Community Development

Faculty of Pure and Applied Sciences

STRUCTURAL CHARACTERIZATION OF ALAMU FIELD NIGER DELTA

BY

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**DEPARTMENT OF GEOLOGY AND MINERAL SCIENCES,
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KWARA STATE UNIVERSITY, MALETE**

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SUPERVISED BY: DR. G. E. OMOLAIYE

SEPTEMBER, 2023.

DECLARATION

This is to certify that this project titled “Structural Characterization of Alamu’s Field, Niger Delta” was carried out and reported by Kehinde Oluwakemi Alamu. I declare that all sources of knowledge gathered had been carefully acknowledged.

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CERTIFICATION

This is to certify that this work was written by KEHINDE OLUWAKEMI ALAMU (20D/57GM/00561) and has been read and approved as meeting one of the requirements of the Department of Geology and Mineral Sciences, Kwara State University, Malete for the award of B.Sc.

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DEDICATION

This is dedicated to the most high GOD the giver of life, to my parents MR AND MRS ALAMU my God caretaker, my spiritual parent PASTOR AND PASTOR MRS ISAIAH, my SIBLINGS for their immense support and love, and finally to my supervisor DR GABRIEL OMOLAIYE.

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ABSTRACT

Subsurface characterization of Alamu field was carried out using 3D seismic data and well logs, the field is one of the prolific assets located in the Niger delta complex. This research addresses difficulties in comprehending complex subsurface fault structures for precise hydrocarbon reserve characterization, lithology identification and structural framework, and petrophysical analysis of Alamu field. The Lithologies and hydrocarbons intervals were initially delineated with the aid of gamma ray, deep resistivity, neutron and density logs of wells. Porosity, shale volume, water saturation, and hydrocarbon saturation of defined reservoirs are revealed by quantitative investigation of the petrophysical evaluation. The gamma ray (GR) logs were normalized and used in the computation of shale volume which ranges from 9.8% - 6.3% using Larinov3, while available density logs were used in the computation of porosities by Bateman-Konen method ranges from 21.6% - 27.2%. Water saturation was determined using the Archie's model to take into consideration the shaly nature of the reservoir sands as well ranges from 16.4% - 23.2%, hydrocarbon saturation ranges from 83.6 % - 76.8%. Twelve faults were interpreted in this study, a network of growth faults and rollover anticlinal structures are also discovered by fault interpretation, adding to the complexity of the subsurface. Horizons were mapped to produce the top structure maps. The structure maps of the tops of the reservoirs revealed that the hydrocarbon structures are fault assisted anticlinal structures and they correspond to the crest of the rollover anticlines on the seismic sections. This study deepens our understanding of subsurface dynamics and provides insightful information for resource assessment and well-informed hydrocarbon exploration decisions.

CHAPTER ONE

1.0 INTRODUCTION

1.1 GENERAL STATEMENT

The oil and gas business has witnessed over the past decade a quantum leap in the effectiveness of geophysics in exploration and production operations. The industry may never have witnessed a technological advancement without the overwhelming impact of 3-D seismic. Real data collection followed by the processing and interpretation of a closely-spaced data volume makes up the 3D seismic data (Kadiri *et al.*, 2020). As Nigerian operations expand into more challenging and costly operating environments (of sound stratigraphic, depositional, and reservoir facies models), a rapidly developing field that makes it easier to create reservoir prediction models connected to important plays is the extraction of facies types using geometric insights and pattern recognition utilizing primarily 3D seismic data. An exploration strategy based on plays that connect local observation to prospect generation is crucial. The derivations of stratigraphic insights from seismic data began in the early 1970s with the advent of improved quality 2D seismic data. The discipline of seismic stratigraphy traces its root to the landmark publication by Vail and his colleagues at Exxon Production Research Company (Vail *et al.*, 1977). The seismic expression of stratigraphic features in a 3D seismic cube depends on which way the data volume is being viewed; vertical transect or horizontal map view.

Seismic profiles provide almost a continuous lateral view of the subsurface by defining its geometry and providing an estimate of the acoustic impedance which is related to the formation

densities and velocities. Structural-stratigraphic integration can allow the spatial correlation of the tectonostratigraphic sequences (Cobos, 2005). Sometimes the estimate of reserves may even be dependent on structural interpretation when fluid contacts located on depth structure maps are needed as inputs in volumetric analysis (Jon and Richard, 2004). Hydrocarbons are found in geologic traps, that is; any combination of rock structures that will keep oil and gas from escaping either vertically or laterally (Wan Qin 1995). However, these traps can either be structural or stratigraphic.

1.2 SCOPE OF THE STUDY

The study area in this research is typically characterized by several growth faults associated with rollover anticlinal structures typical of the Niger Delta extensional zone (Doust and Omatsola, 1990). Crestal accumulations below mature erosion surface, canyon-fill accumulation above unconformity surface, and facies change traps are the stratigraphic accumulations recognized in the Niger Delta. The area of study, ALAMU'S Field', is located in the coastal swamp depobelt, Niger Delta Basin with the field containing about 6 wells.

1.3 STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

Poor understanding of complex faulted subsurface configuration often leads to erroneous deductions or the reservoir geometry (Akinwunmi *et al.*, 2004). To understand the complicated subsurface geology for hydrocarbon exploration in the study area, detailed seismic interpretation and petrophysical evaluation were performed.

1.4 AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

The purpose of this study is to carry out detailed subsurface evaluation of Alamu asset.

The objectives of this project are as follows:

1. To identify lithologies using gamma-ray logs.
2. To correlate the reservoirs across the study area
3. To create the structural framework of the study area
4. To carry out a petrophysical evaluation of reservoirs A, B, and C.

1.5 LITERATURE REVIEW

Structural and stratigraphic characterization of different hydrocarbon-bearing fields have been widely studied by various researchers, among which are; Mariam *et al.*, (2021), carried out a systematic and process-based incorporation of seismic and well logs datasets to characterize the structural and stratigraphic framework of sandstone reservoirs within the field in order to determine their capacities for effective CO₂ sequestration. Petrophysical analysis, fault modeling as well as geostatistical techniques were used to build facies and property models which enabled a qualitative assessment of the sealing potential of faults associated with the reservoirs based on the prediction of key properties such as shale gouge ratio, lithological juxtaposition, fault permeability and fault transmissibility across the fault faces. Nine water-bearing sandstone reservoirs (reservoirs A–J) with varying reservoir quality were identified in the field. The dominance of high SGR, low permeability, higher fault throws, and low fault transmissibility values at the lower parts of the faults indicate the deeper structural traps of the field are low-risk zones and might serve as good storage areas for CO₂.

Sadun (2002), adopted the use of 3-D seismic data and well logs to characterize structural and depositional settings of the Guasare-Misoa interval. Three main seismic reflectors, which are the Late Eocene unconformity, Guasare, and La Luna formations, were picked. The most dominant structure in the area is the VLE 400 Fault which was interpreted as a left-lateral strike-slip reverse fault due to its behaviors as a reverse fault in cross sections and as a strike-slip fault in strike sections.

Leonardo *et al.*, (2017), this study was aim to approach the trapping mechanisms that act in the Eocene turbidites of the Carapebus Formation, in the Southwest portion of Campos Basin. 2D and 3D seismic data were analyzed, as well as well data distributed along six oil fields: Pampo, Trilha, West Enchova, Enchova, Bicudo, and Bonito. The main Eocene deposit was observed in 16 of the 19 analyzed wells, showing the highest thicknesses between 90 m and 100 m in the South-central region of Bonito Field. Two main areas with economic potential were found: one in the Western area of the Bicudo field, structural traps are dominant, while the border region between Enchova and Bonito fields is characterized by an association of structural and stratigraphic traps.

Anomneze *et al.*, (2015), Application of seismic stratigraphy and structural analysis in the determination of petroleum plays within the Eastern Niger Delta Basin, Nigeria. This study has aided the identification and description of three plays: (1) Shelf edge play (2) Pinch-out play (3) Hanging wall play. The shelf-edge deltas revealed the preservation of LST stacked sands with thickness of greater than 300 ft each below a wedge-shaped facies that is shale-prone. In a vertical transect section this stacked sand thickens more landwards, showing a wedge-shaped

geometry and a structural drag while in a map view it displays an aguacate geometry showing a broader extent of the reservoir towards the much distal position. This reservoir is bounded by a counter re-gional fault which also serves as migration pathway with charge from a lower Akata source rock. The pinch out of sand units is predicted to occur when reflectors pinch out away from areas of sequence thickening. Good reservoir quality is inferred to be present almost to the pinch-out limit of sand units and is trapped by inter-reservoir shale as a result of the stratigraphic trapping system and not facies change. The hanging wall trap exists predominantly around closely spaced listric faults at the distal end of a Depobelt. They often arise due to rotation of fault blocks up-dip as sedimentation moves basinward and the associated reservoirs display a spherical shape on map view. The major seal within these plays is the regional maximum flooding surfaces and inter-reservoir shale.

Obiekezie *et al.*, (2015), evaluated the hydrocarbon-bearing zones of OTU'S field. Three horizons, C10, D10, and D31 were identified and mapped to produce the structure maps. The structure maps of the tops of the reservoirs revealed that the hydrocarbon structures are fault-assisted anticlinal structures and they correspond to the crest of the rollover anticlines on the seismic sections. The RMS amplitude attribute extracted on the surfaces revealed bright spots on the region of the anticlinal structures which indicates that the field has economically explorable hydrocarbons accumulations. The net thickness of the reservoir varies between 45 ft and 273 ft.

Aizebeokhai *et al.*, (2010), carried out structural and stratigraphic mapping of Emi Field, using the integration of seismic and well data to determine the field's subsurface geometry,

stratigraphy, and hydrocarbon trapping potential. The lithological units were identified on the logs and correlated through the wells. The generated stratigraphic sections show the general continuity of the lithological units through the topography. Seismic well linkages reveal that high-amplitude reflection events correspond to sand units, while low-amplitude reflection events correspond to shale units. Four horizons, H1, H2, H3, and H4 were interpreted within Agbada Formation and considered to be good hydrocarbon prospects. Stratigraphic plays such as pinch, unconformities, sand lenses, and channels are also suspected. Integrating seismic data with well logs has proven to be a useful tool for structural and stratigraphic mapping as well as for predicting horizontal and vertical variations of lithological units.

Hussein *et al.*, (2021), calibrated and defined seismic profile with well log data (check shot, well top, density log, and sonic log) within the study area to determine the limit top and base of the Yammama Formation. The maps help to understand the horizontal and vertical changes configuration of the subsurface. The seismic interpretation of the area confirms the presence of several stratigraphic features in the studied formation. The study revealed that the thickness of Yammama increased eastward, meaning it increased from the Abu-Amoud field at Nasiriyah towards the East Abu-Amoud field in Missan. Stratified traps were identified using seismic attributes (relative acoustic impedance) in the East Abu-Amoud field.

G. E Omolaiye *et al.*, (2016). The main objective of this study is to perform geophysical and petrophysical interpretations of properties that are typical of a shallow marine, transitional environment, with its attendant pattern of subsurface complexities, using 3D seismic and well log data. The approach adopted in achieving this objective included 3D seismic data

interpretation, petrophysical rock typing, fluid typing and contact identification and determination of reservoir properties, onwards to reserve estimation for all the hydrocarbon-bearing reservoirs in the field. Five horizons as well as major and minor faults were mapped in the field, and five structural depth maps of reservoirs A, B, B1, C and C1 were generated within the objective depth interval to define the geometry of the reservoirs. Well log data from four wells in the field were studied to characterize the porosity, shale volume and water saturation of the reservoirs. However, within the reservoirs of Tadelu field, the net sand range is from 0.17 to 0.99 ft, having an average porosity in the range of 22 to 27 %. Water saturation average ranged from a minimum of 19 to a maximum of 27 %. Porosity in the field is high on the average due to very good to excellent sand quality. The gross rock volume (GRV) was determined by establishing a cut-off at appropriate contact(s). Reserve estimation was performed for the hydrocarbon-bearing sands and a total proven recoverable oil and gas estimate put at 42.797 MMbbl and 13.256 Bscf, respectively.

CHAPTER TWO

2.0 GEOLOGY OF NIGERIA

Nigeria is located in West Africa and is bordered by Niger to the north, Chad to the northeast, Cameroon to the south, and the Republic of Benin to the west. With a population of over 200 million people, it is the most populous country in Africa and is known as the "Giant of Africa" (Obaje 2009).

It is a multi-ethnic country with more than 250 ethnic groups and more than 500 languages spoken. However, three of her ethnic groups stand out in the crowd: Hausa-Fulani to the north, Yoruba to the west, and Igbo to the east. It makes up over 70% of the population (Kästle 2022). The diversity of languages and ethnicities made communication between groups extremely difficult, but the adoption of English as the official language made this problem easier. However, the three largest groups of languages are also widely spoken, and it's not uncommon to find someone who speaks all three languages fluently. Pidgin English is also the lingua franca of Nigeria (Ajayi *et al.*). Christianity is the predominant religion in the south and Islam is the predominant religion in the north. The percentage of followers of each religion is distributed about half of the population. However, a minority of people practice their indigenous religion. Nigeria lies approximately between latitudes 4 and 154N and longitudes 34 and 14E, within the Pan-African mobile belt between the West African and Congo cratons (Fig. 1). Nigeria's geology is dominated by three major rock types. Both crystalline (igneous and metamorphic) and sedimentary rocks occur in approximately equal proportions. Crystalline igneous and metamorphic rocks form the Precambrian-Palaeozoic bedrock complex that occurs in the eastern region of the country, which extends from north-central to northeastern Nigeria. The sedimentary basins consist of seven inland basins: the Niger Delta, Anambra, Benue Trough, Chad, Sokoto, Bida Nupe, and Dahomey Basins, all of which consist of sediment which are of different ages from the Cretaceous to recent period.

The geology of Nigeria began in the Archean and Proterozoic eras of the Precambrian. The country forms the state of Nigeria, and more than half of its surface consists of Precambrian

igneous and metamorphic crystalline bedrock. Between 2.9 and 500 million years ago, three major orogenic events and associated magmatic intrusions impacted Nigeria. After the pan-African orogeny, Nigeria experienced regional sedimentation and witnessed new igneous intrusions accompanied by the proliferation of multicellular organisms. During the Late Mesozoic Cretaceous, massive transgression generated large-scale sediments in various basins. During the Eocene, in the Cenozoic epochs, the terrestrial condition of the region returned.

Fig 1: Map of Nigeria

2.1.1 NIGERIA BASEMENT COMPLEX

The basement complex is one of the three major litho-petrological components that make up Nigeria's geology (Fig. 2). The Nigerian Bases Complex is part of the Pan-African Moving Belt, between the West African and Congo cratons, south of the Tuareg Shield (Black, 1980). It is intruded by the Mesozoic calc-alkaline ring complexes (Younger Granites) of the Jos Plateau and is unconformably overlain by Cretaceous and younger sediments. The Nigerian basement was influenced by the pan-African orogeny 600 million years ago, in a revitalized region resulting from a plate collision between the passive West African cratonic margin and the active phallic margin. (Burke and Dewey, 1972; Dada, 2006)). This basement rock has undergone deformation, metamorphism, and remobilization of at least four major orogenic cycles, corresponding to the Liberian (2,700 Ma), Eburnean (2,000 Ma), Kibaran (1,100 Ma), and Pan-African stages (600 Ma). The first three cycles were characterized by intense deformation and isoclinic folding with local metamorphism, followed by extensive migration. Pan-African deformation was accompanied by regional metamorphism, migmatization, and extensive granitization and gneissification, producing syntectonic granites and homogeneous gneisses (Abaa, 1983). Late tectonic emplacement of granites and granodiorites and associated contact metamorphism accompanied the end stages of this last deformation. The end of the orogeny was marked by faulting and fracturing (Gandu *et al.*, 1986; Olayinka, 1992). Within the basement complex of Nigeria four major petro-lithological units are distinguishable, namely:

1. The Migmatite – Gneiss Complex (MGC)
2. The Schist Belt (Metasedimentary and Metavolcanic rocks)

3. The Older Granites (Pan African granitoids)

4. Undeformed Acid and Basic Dykes

Fig 2: Geological sketch map of Nigeria showing the major geological components of Basement complex, Younger Granite, and sedimentary basin

2.2 GEOLOGY OF NIGER DELTA

The Niger Delta Basin, also referred to as the Niger Delta province, is an extensional rift basin located in the Niger Delta and the Gulf of Guinea on the passive continental margin near the western coast of Nigeria (Tuttle *et al.*, 2015) with suspected or proven access to Cameroon, Equatorial Guinea and São Tomé and Príncipe. In the World, the main productive deltaic

hydrocarbon province is known to be the Niger Delta basin and is the most substantial basin in the West Africa continent margin. The Niger Delta basin is one of the largest subaerial basins in Africa. It has a subaerial area of about 75,000 km², a total area of 300,000 km², and a sediment fill of 500,000 km³ (Fatoke & Ademola 2010). It is composed of different geologic formations that indicate how this basin could have formed, as well as the regional and large-scale tectonics of the area.

The Niger Delta Basin was formed by a failed rift junction during the separation of the South American plate and the African plate, as the South Atlantic began to open. Rifting in this basin started in the late Jurassic and ended in the mid-Cretaceous. The Niger Delta Basin is an extensional basin surrounded by many other basins in the area that all formed from similar processes.

The sediment fill in the Niger Delta basin fill has a depth between 9–12 km. It is composed of several geologic formations that indicate how this basin could have formed, as well as the regional and large-scale tectonics of the area. The sediment is characterized by three major depobelts. These three cycles show that the basin experienced an overall regression throughout time as the sediments go from deep-sea mud-sized grains to fluvial denser sand-sized grains. The lithologies of the area experience change due to several factors. The sediment provenance from the onshore highlands which feed into the delta controls the mineralogy of the grains. Additionally, the impact of sea level on sediment deposition is well known; relative sea level will control the basinward extent of lithologies. Volcanic activity in the area may also result in thin deposits of ash (bentonite). The early Cretaceous sediments are

thought to be from a tide-dominated system that was deposited on a concave shoreline, and throughout time the shoreline became convex and it is currently a wave-dominated system. Niger Delta oil and gas are predominantly trapped by rollover anticlines and fault closures. Stratigraphic traps of paleo-channel fill, regional sand pinch-outs and truncations, crestal accumulations below unconformity surfaces, canyon-fill accumulations above unconformity surfaces, incised valley and low-stand fans have been recognized (Orife and Avbovbo, 1982; Kruse and Idiagbor, 1994). Hydrocarbon distribution in the Niger Delta is complex with a gas-to-oil ratio generally increasing southward away from the depocentre within a depobelt (Evamy *et al.*, 1978) and is primarily controlled by the thermal history of the source rocks, source rocks quality, migration, and sealing quality. In addition, the timing of trap formation could be a factor that controls the distribution of hydrocarbon (Chukwueke, 1997).

The Niger Delta Province contains only one identified petroleum system (Kulke, 1995; Ekweozor and Daukoru, 1994). This system is referred to here as the Tertiary Niger Delta (Akata-Agbada) Petroleum System. Petroleum occurs throughout the Agbada Formation in the Niger Delta clastic wedge. Although the distribution of hydrocarbons is complex, there is a general tendency for the ratio of gas to oil to increase southward within individual depobelts (Doust and Omatsola, 1989). Gas-to-oil ratios within reservoirs were reported by Evamy *et al.* (1978), Ejedawe (1981), and Doust and Omatsola (1990). Reservoirs occur along northwest-southeast “oil-rich belts” and along a number of north-south trends in the Port Harcourt area. Tuttle *et al.* (1999) suggest that belts roughly correspond to the transition between continental and oceanic crust within the axis of maximum sediment thickness. Other authors have related oil-rich belts to structural or depositional controls, to an increase in the geothermal gradient, and shifts in

deposition basin ward within subsequent depobelts (Ejedawe, 1981; Weber, 1986; Doust and Omatsola, 1990; Haacket *al.*, 1997). The maximum extent of the petroleum system coincides with the boundaries of the province. The minimum extent of the system is defined by the areal extent of fields and contains known resources (cumulative production plus proved reserves) of 34.5 billion barrels of oil (BBO) and 93.8 trillion cubic feet of gas (TCFG) (14.9 billion barrels of oil equivalent, BBOE) (Petroconsultants, 1996a). Stacher (1995) developed a hydrocarbon habitat model based on sequence stratigraphy of some petroleum-rich belts within the Niger Delta area and provides a short summary of basin, trap, reservoir, source rock, and hydrocarbon character (Table 1)

The Niger Delta is a hydrocarbon province with ultimate recovery presently estimated at nearly 40 billion barrels of oil. This is about 70% of the overall hydrocarbon reserves of sub-Saharan Africa. The gas reserves are conservatively estimated at over 40 trillion cubic feet. The hydrocarbon was sourced from marine shales with land plant materials giving rise to mainly Types III and II/III organic matter within an oil window that varied in depth from 9,000 to 14,000 ft. The reservoirs are mainly shoreface, beach, and channel sands bearing low sulphur /nickel, light waxy, nondegraded oils. Light crude-bearing deeper reservoirs have also been substantiated in some inland blocks. (Mosunmolu Limited, 2014).

Fig 3: Schematic map of the Niger Delta showing the distribution of depositional and structural belts (modified after Whiteman (1982), Damuth (1994), and Cohen and McClay (1996))

Table I: Hydrocarbon habitat table. Modified from Stacher (1995).

Geology	Tropical delta at passive continental margin of south Atlantic; Early Tertiary to recent age; Mostly shallow ramp depositional model; Shelf break locally mappable.
Traps	Dip closures (rollover anticline in growth faults); Fault bound traps; Stratigraphic traps (truncation Traps; Stratigraphic traps (truncation traps, tidal Deltas, channels etc.).
Reservoir	Deltaic sandstones (shoreface, beach, channel etc); Stacked sand/shale alternations; Multi-reservoir fields; Reservoir depth 5000-14000 ft.
Source rock	Marine shales (Akata shales) with land plant material (high potential); Type III/II, III vitrinite Liptinite, S.O.M; within well penetrations measured VR less than 0.7; Top oil window variable 9000-14000 ft.
Hydrocarbons	Oil/condensate/gas; Gravity 15-25 API biodegraded; Gravity 25-45 API non-bio-degraded; Low sulphur/nickel; Pristane/Phythane ratio 0.6-1.6; Rich in waxes/resins, other land plant material S.O.M.

2.3 STRATIGRAPHY OF NIGER DELTA

Although the stratigraphy of the Niger Delta clastic wedge has been documented during oil exploration and production, most stratigraphic schemes remain proprietary to the major oil companies operating concessions in the Niger Delta Basin. According to Obafemi *et al.*, 2020 the Niger Delta Basin stratigraphy is mainly composed of three lithostratigraphic units. These units are shown in Fig. 4, include the Akata Formation of the lowest oceanic delta front, the Agbada Formation of the mid-shallow oceanic delta front, and the overlying Benin Formation of the recent continental delta plain (Doust and Omatsola 1990; Adojoh *et al.*, 2020). The Akata Formation is composed of marine delta shale and turbid sand with a small amount of silt. There

are no drill holes that reach the bottom of the Akata Formation, but one bottomless drill hole penetrates the Akata Formation approximately 3658 feet. (Sanuade *et al.*, 2017). Cretaceous shale lies uncomfortably on bedrock up to 2,000 feet thick on land and can reach 6,550 feet offshore the Niger Delta (Bellingham *et al.* 2014). The Akata Formation formed in a progressive depression approximately 21,000 feet thick in the central portion of the clastic wedge characterized by low oxygen supply and low-energy conditions (Stacher 1995). This load compacted the underlying shale of the Akata Formation into a shale diapir. The Agbada Formation overlies the Akata Formation, was deposited in the Eocene, and is still being deposited by diachronous deposition in the Niger Delta Basin (Short and Stäuble 1967). The Agbada Formation is a transition zone and represents the delta region of the Niger Delta. This formation consists of a succession of sand and shale (paralic siliceous rock) up to 13,000 feet thick. It constitutes the main hydrocarbon reservoir in the Niger delta (Tuttle *et al.* 1999). The Benin Formation consists of the most recent sediments of the delta, deposited from the Eocene to the Holocene. This formation is mainly composed of alluvial sand about 4600 feet thick (Avbovbo 1978; Obaje 2009). The Benin Formation acts as an overlying rock in the Niger Delta (Sanuade *et al.* 2017)

Fig 4: The stratigraphic column showing the three formations of the Niger Delta and variable density seismic display of the main stratigraphic units with corresponding reflections (Lawrence et.al 2002; Corridor et. al., 2005)

2.4 STRUCTURAL TRAPS IN NIGER DELTA

The dominant subsurface structures in the Niger delta are the syn- and post- sedimentary listric and growth faults, which affect the main delta sequence. The growth fault system is a series of major growing faults that increase in space and become younger as the delta prograde southwards (Doust and Omatsola 1989). The growth faults which formed the structural traps developed during syn-sedimentary deformation of the Agbada paralic sequence (Evamy *et al.*, 1978; Stacher, 1995). Doust & Omatsola (1990) described a variety of structural trapping elements, including those associated with simple rollover structures; structures with multiple growth faults, structures with antithetic faults, and collapsed crest structures (Fig 5). (Hosper 1971; Merki 1972) also identified some structural features that are also associated with the growth fault systems, such as; shale ridges, and shale diapirs. The syn-sedimentary structures produced from the gravity sliding during sedimentation cause structural complexity in the Niger Delta (Basile *et al.* 2005). Growth faults are the most common structural features observed on seismic sections of the Niger Delta (Onyia V *et al.*, 2002). Mud diapirs are the most common and occur on the landward side of the growth faults restricting sedimentation on the up-thrown side of the faults and enhancing sedimentation on the down-thrown side. Most of the faults are listric normal; others include structures building growth faults, crestal faults, flank faults, counter-regional faults, and antithetic faults. Trap configuration in the offshore Niger Delta is controlled by gravity driven systems of linked extensional growth faults and compressional toe thrusts initiated during the Paleocene when the modern Niger Delta was formed (Duncan and Townsend, 1997). The growth faults led to lateral variations in reservoir thickness (Tuttle *et al.* 1999). Sand is found in stacked channels and point bars, distributary channels, and coastal

barrier bars, while the main trap type in the Niger Delta is structural traps such as rollover anticlines (Owoyemi and Willis 2006). The interbedded shale smear along the faults acts as a horizontal seal, while the shale also represents the vertical seal for the sand reservoirs in the Agbada Formation (Doust and Omatsola 1990; Abdel-Fattah *et al.* 2019). In the Niger Delta, the growth faults represent the pathways for hydrocarbons from the Akata Formation to the Agbada Formation (Tuttle *et al.* 1999).

Fig 5: Major structures and associated traps in Niger Delta. Modified from Doust and Omatsola (1990) and Stacher (1995).

CHAPTER THREE

3.0 DATASET AND METHODOLOGY

The material used in the cause of this study include; 3D seismic data, Six well data with suite of wireline logs such as gamma ray, resistivity, porosity and sonic, Checkshot data and Well deviation data.

Fig 6: Base map of the research area showing the well locations

Table II: Inventory of well data used for the Study

	ALAMU 01	ALAMU 02	ALAMU 03	ALAMU 04	ALAMU 05	ALAMU 06
LOGS						
DEPTH	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
CALI	✓	•	✓	✓	✓	✓
GR	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
RES (LLD/LLS/R T/MSFL)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
RHOB (DRHO)	•	•	✓	✓	✓	✓
NPHI	•	•	✓	✓	✓	✓
DT (DTU/DTL)	•	•	•	✓	✓	•
LITH	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

PHIE	✓	•	✓	✓	✓	✓
SP	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
SW	✓	•	✓	✓	✓	✓

WELL INVENTORY

3.1 PETROPHYSICAL EVALUATION

Gamma ray log was used in lithology identification (sand and shale), resistivity log was used in identification of reservoirs while the porosity tools (neutron and density log) was used in identification of the type of fluid present in the reservoir i.e. oil from gas. Some petrophysical properties of the reservoir rocks and fluid characters such as porosity, shale volume, effective porosity, permeability, and formation resistivity factor, resistivity of water, water saturation, and net pay thickness were evaluated.

3.1.1 RESERVOIR AND FLUID IDENTIFICATION

The reservoir is the only area with potential economic benefit because it contains storage spaces that allow fluid (hydrocarbons or water) to accumulate there. A good hydrocarbon reservoir should be porous, permeable, and also contain hydrocarbons. In this study, reservoir rock was determined by interpreting the available log data. The gamma-ray log used to identify reservoir rock is based on the fact that the sandstone-bearing rock are non-radioactive while shale contain radioactive materials. Resistivity logs were used to discriminate high resistivity typify hydrocarbon from low resistive zone which is indicative of saline water.

3.1.2 POROSITY

Porosity is a very important parameter for the characterization of the reservoir rock as it is used to describe the amount of open space filled with fluid (hydrocarbon or water). Porosity is classified into two and they are; Total porosity and Effective porosity. The shale volume versus effective porosity cross plot enabled the estimation of the shale distribution patterns present in the reservoir and as well as their effects in the reservoir. Both are calculated as the follows:

Total porosity calculation is done by the combination of neutron–density logs, the total porosity within reservoirs interval was determined. The equation to compute the total porosity from neutron and density logs that may be expressed as:

$$\Phi_{tot} = \frac{(\Phi_N + \Phi_D)}{2} \quad 1$$

Where Φ_N = Neutron porosity,

Φ_D = Density porosity

$$\Phi_D = \frac{(\rho_{ma} - \rho_b)}{(\rho_{ma} - \rho_f)} \quad 2$$

Where ρ_b : bulk density which includes both fluid and rock (read directly from the log), ρ_f : density of the saturating fluid, ρ_{ma} : density of the rock matrix, ϕ : porosity.

According to Baker H (1992) the criteria for classifying porosity is as follows:

$\phi < 0.05$	Negligible
$0.05 < \phi < 0.1$	Poor
$0.1 < \phi < 0.15$	Fair
$0.15 < \phi < 0.25$	Good
$0.25 < \phi < 0.30$	Very good
$\phi > 0.30$	Excellent.

The effective porosity is usually based on an adjustment of total porosity by means of estimated shale volume.

$$\Phi_{eff} = \Phi_T - (\Phi_{sh} \times V_{sh}) \quad 3$$

Where Φ_{eff} = effective porosity,

Φ_T = total porosity,

Φ_{sh} = porosity reading in a shale zone,

V_{sh} = Shale volume.

3.1.3 VOLUME OF SHALE

Calculation of shale volume is crucial because it helps to estimate volume of shale, clay presence in the reservoir. In this study, the volume of shale was estimated using a gamma ray logs method as the following equation

$$IGR = \frac{(GR_{log} - GR_{min})}{(GR_{max} - GR_{min})} \quad 4$$

Where, IGR = Gamma ray Index,

GRlog = gamma ray reading of the formation,

GRmin = minimum gamma ray, maximum density log reading,

IGR = Vsh in the linear model

3.1.4 WATER SATURATION

According to the society of Petroleum Engineers 2023, it is known that complexities is likely to arise in the estimation of the water saturation parameter because there are a number of independent approaches that can be used to calculate S_w . These different approaches lead to somewhat different S_w values that may equate to considerable differences in the original oil in place (OOIP) or original gas in place (OGIP) volumes. The challenge to the technical team is to resolve and to understand the differences among the S_w values obtained using the different procedures, and to arrive at the best calculation of S_w and its distribution throughout the reservoir vertically. In OOIP and OGIP calculations, it is important to remember the relative importance of porosity and S_w . A 10% pore volume (PV) change in S_w has the same impact as a 2% bulk volume (BV) change in porosity (in a 20% BV porosity reservoir).

The technique chosen to calculate S_w is often a hybrid that combines the use of any of basic data sources. For example, the oil-based mud (OBM)-core S_w data can be used in combination with the resistivity logs to expand the data set used to include all wells and the whole of the hydrocarbon column. Alternatively, the OBM-core S_w data can be used in combination with the P_c/S_w data. In this way, the OBM-core S_w data define the S_w values for the majority of the reservoir, whereas the P_c/S_w data define the S_w values in the interval just above the fluid contact and perhaps in areas of the field where P_c data are available but OBM-core data are not.

Ideally a typical hydrocarbon reservoir contains the 3 components, gas, Oil and water in that stratification order, with lower water content indicating higher hydrocarbon. Therefore, estimating the amount of water saturation is key in quantifying the amount of hydrocarbon in

place, while the resistivity log identifies the hydrocarbon column above the fluid contacts. The net to gross provided by the gamma ray log together with the porosity is combined to compute the amount of hydrocarbon in place. In this study, water saturation was estimated using Archie's model, the relationship between the resistivity of formation water and porosity as shown in the empirical relationship in Equation below:

$$S_w = \frac{a \times R_w}{(R_t \times \phi^m)^{\frac{1}{n}}} \quad 5$$

Where; S_w = water saturation of the uninvaded zone,

S_h = hydrocarbon saturation,

R_t = true formation resistivity (from LLD log curve),

ϕ = porosity values obtained from a porosity log,

R_w = resistivity of formation water.

3.1.5 NET TO GROSS

The Gross reservoir thickness is the total interval recognized as the reservoir interval, including regions occupied by sandstone and clays within a reservoir. This thickness is determined using lithology tool (gamma ray log). Net sand thickness, on the other hand, is the interval of the reservoir occupied by sand alone. The net sand thickness was determined by subtracting the

thickness of shale/clay baffle within a reservoir thickness. The expressions used for mapping out interval thicknesses in the wells studied are shown as follows.

$$GST = \text{Gross and thickness}(\text{Base of sand} - \text{Top of sand}) \quad 6$$

$$NST = \text{Nets and thickness}(\text{Base} + \text{top of sand} - \text{Thickness of shale baffle}) \quad 7$$

Therefore, Net to gross is estimated from; $NTG = \frac{NST}{GST}$ 8

Net reservoir thickness (h) can be calculated by using the following formula:

$$h = H - h_{shale} \quad 9$$

Where H= The gross reservoir thickness,

h_{shale} =The thicknesses of the shale

Where NST is h

GST is H

3.2 SEISMIC ACQUISITION

Seismic data acquisition involves applying a seismic energy source, such as a vibroseis truck or shot-hole dynamite at discrete surface location. The resulting energy is reflected back from interfaces where rock properties change. By recording this reflected energy at an array of geophones placed in the ground surface, the results can be processed to produce an image of underground geological structures and a range of attributes that can be used to infer the physical rock properties. Surveys can be conducted along lines to produce a vertical profile (**2D survey**)

or over an area to generate a **3D** sub-surface volume. Time-lapse or **4D** seismic surveying. Relies upon change in physical properties (i.e. impedance contrast).

3.3 SEISMIC PROCESSING

The sequence of processing from raw seismic data to final forms ready for interpretation has evolved over the years, and many general aspects of the sequence have become more-or-less conventional. It is a non-trivial matter to design a proper sequence of seismic data processing, called a processing flow. Figure 7. shows an example of a processing flow for reflection seismic data more than 30 years ago (W. A. Schneider, unpublished class notes, 1977). The general procedure shown in this figure still holds true for today's processing flow for making post-stack sections. The goal of seismic data processing is to help interpretation, the process of deciphering the useful information contained in the data. The task is to transfer the raw data into a form that is optimal for extracting the signal. The word "optimal" implies making the best choice after considering all factors. Hence, we need to make decisions in the process of seismic data analysis, because reflection seismic energy arrive later, it might be obscured by another seismic signals like ground roll and direct waves. Hence, we apply Seismic data Processing to remove unwanted signals and noises and to enhance signal to noise ratio.

All methods of seismic data analysis rely on physical and geological theories that tie the seismic data and the geological problem together. For instance, a problem of inferring aligned fractures may involve the theory of seismic anisotropy. The subsequent data processing will attempt to utilize this theory to extract the signal of the fracture. Alteration of seismic data to suppress noise, enhance signal and migrate seismic events to the appropriate location in space is termed as

Seismic Processing. It facilitates better interpretation because subsurface structures and reflection geometries are more apparent.

Fig 7: A general processing flow, after Schneider (unpublished class notes from 1977). Steps c, d, and e are usually iterated to test different hypotheses. Pre-stack processing is often conducted after a post-stack processing to help the velocity model building process. There are also reports of pre-stack processing using limited offsets to increase the efficiency.

3.4 SEISMIC INTERPRETATION

Seismic interpretation was carried out using Petrel software. Time, depth and amplitude maps were generated and analyzed.

3.4.1 WELL CORRELATION

The available gamma-ray, resistivity logs and porosity tools from the oil wells in the field were used for well correlation and reservoirs delineation. The deflections of the gamma ray signature to the left (low values) of the shale baseline is indicative sandstone while the deflection to the right (high values) signifies shale. High resistivity values corresponding with sandstone zone is interpreted as a reservoir while low resistivity values represent shale or reservoir containing saltwater

3.4.2 STRUCTURAL SMOOTHENING

A structural smoothening cube was generated to enhance the continuity of seismic reflections (Fig. 8). Structural smoothing is a very important process because it helps to remove noise and artefacts from the seismic data. This process is used to create a more accurate representation of the subsurface structure by removing small-scale features that are not geologically significant. It is also used to improve the resolution of the seismic data by reducing the impact of acquisition and processing artefacts. The structural smoothening allows the accurate mapping of faults, rapid identification of critical flowing or sealing windows along the faults, better integration of fault properties and geometrics within the simulator.

(Original seismic line)

(After applying structural smoothing)

Fig 8: Seismic section showing the fault both the original seismic line and the structural smoothing for fault identification.

3.4.3 VARIANCE (EDGE DETECTION) METHOD

Furthermore, variance time slice (Fig. 9) taken from the generated variance volume were used to visualize and observe the lateral distribution and orientation of the different faults within the field to accurately and succinctly capture and define the fault styles and the associated trapping structures. Detailed identification and mapping of faults were done from the seismic line using time slices from 3D variance volume attributes and vertical sections from the structurally filtered volume. The variance attribute uses an algorithm that computes the local variance of the seismic

data through a multi-trace window with user-defined size. It helps in enhancing edge detection by emphasizing larger and planer features. Its helps to identify up thrown and downthrown sides of a fault.

(Un-interpreted)

Fig 9: Variance edge showing the fault interpreted in the field

3.4.4 FAULT PICKING

A fault is a break in the continuity of any geologic unit, which involved either a lateral or vertical movement of any part of the rock unit, caused by varying geologic processes. Faults can be delineated as abrupt termination of reflection events or displacement or distortion of reflection. Faults are easier to identify on the dip section. Interpreted fault were quality checked and fixed/assigned.

3.4.5 GENERATION OF SYNTHETIC SEISMOGRAM

A synthetic seismogram is the fundamental link between well data and seismic data, and it is the main tool (along with a vertical seismic profile [VSP], if available) that allows geological picks to be associated with reflections in the seismic data. As discussed, if a VSP is available for a particular well, a synthetic is not needed. Synthetic seismograms were created by convolving reflectance obtained from sonic and density logs and wavelets obtained from seismic data. Sonic logs were calibrated (corrected) with checkshots before being combined with density logs to determine reflection coefficients. Synthetic seismograms were used to link well data and seismic data. This relationship formed the first step in selecting events corresponding to sand tops for interpretation. First, a sonic calibration was carried out in order to combine the accuracy of the check shot data with the detail of the sonic log to get the best possible time–depth relationship (TDR). The new TDR becomes active for the well, and it was used for the synthetic generation process. The wavelet used was estimated from the seismic data 50 meter radius around Alamu - 4 well

Overall, the result shows a good tie as no shift was done to tie the synthetic to the seismic data.

The steps necessary to create a synthetic seismogram manually are described below:

1. Edit the sonic and density logs for bad intervals.
2. Calculate vertical reflection times.
3. Calculate reflection coefficients, R_0 .
4. Combine the last two items to create a reflection coefficient time series.

5. Convolve the reflection coefficient series with the wavelet

1.1.6 HORIZON MAPPING

The horizons were interpreted consistently based on well-tie analysis. All interpretations were made on the same in-line/cross-line interval. Interpretation was done only where the horizons are defined and not in highly uncertain areas. Areas of interpretation uncertainty were separated from other areas by using separate seismic grids (or surface. Fault picking, horizon mapping and loop linking were done manually using Petrel software. Horizons were interpreted from peaks and tracked throughout the seismic volume, this was done on every 10 inline and crossline intervals to generate a seismic seed grid.

Fig 10: Structural smoothing showing the interpreted faults and horizons

CHAPTER FOUR

2.0 RESULT AND DISCUSSION

2.1 POTENTIAL RESERVOIR IDENTIFICATION

The three main permeable interesting zones identified in Alamu 4 well named reservoirs A, B, C and D (Figs. 11 – 13). These zones were characterized by the low gamma ray response, relatively high porosity, neutron–density crossover, and high resistivity value. The generated cross-plots Fig. 14 indicate that the main lithology is shaly sandstone in reservoirs A, B, and C.

Fig 11: The composite layout showing Reservoir A

Fig 12: The composite layout showing Reservoir B

Fig 13: The composite layout showing Reservoir C

Fig 14: Density–neutron–gamma ray cross-plot of the main reservoir (C, B, & A zone) in Alamu well - 4

2.2 QUANTITATIVE ANALYSIS

The three interpreted reservoirs across the study area lies within the depth interval of 3389 to 3432 m (RES_A), 3213 to 3230 m (RES_B), and 2914 to 2924 m (RES_C), with thicknesses

ranging from 44, 17, and 10 m, respectively (Figs. 11, 12, 13). The three hydrocarbon zones were analyzed quantitatively to estimate for shale volume, porosity, and water saturation, net pay by using empirical formulas as described in the methodology above. The average total porosity results are: 21.6 % (RES_A), 21.9 % (RES_B), and 27.2 % (RES_C). The average shale volume estimated from the gamma ray log was found to be 9.8 %, 6.4 % and 6.3 % for RES_A, RES_B and RES_C respectively. The calculated value of average water saturation using Archie equation is 16.4 % for RES_A, 20.9 % for RES_B and 23.2 % for RES_C. On the other hand, we used the average water saturation values to estimate the value of hydrocarbon saturation, which is ranged from 83.6 % for RES_A, 79.1 % for RES_B and 76.8 % for the RES_C. All petrophysical parameters estimated for the hydrocarbon-bearing zones and net pay are shown in Table III and Figs 15 – 20.

Fig 15: Water saturation picking using picket plot for RES_A

Fig 16: Water saturation picking using picket plot for RES_B

Fig 17: Water saturation picking using picket plot for RES_C

Fig 18: Calculated petrophysical parameters of the main reservoir (RES_A zone) along the Alamu 4 well

Fig 19: Calculated petrophysical parameters of the main reservoir (RES_B zone) along the Alamu 4 well

Fig 20: Calculated petrophysical parameters of the main reservoir (RES_C zone) along the Alamu 4 well

Table III: The pay summary

WELL	INTERVAL	DEPTH_TOP	DEPTH_BASE	GROSS	NET	NET_TO_GROSS	PHIE_AV	VSH_GM	SWE_AV
		METRES	METRES	METRES	METRES	M/M	%	%	%
ALAMU_4	RES_C	2914.369	2924.106	9.737	3.2	0.329	27.2	6.3	23.2
ALAMU_4	RES_B	3212.819	3229.858	17.039	11.704	0.687	21.9	6.4	20.9
ALAMU_4	RES_A	3388.608	3432.952	44.344	30.546	0.689	21.6	9.8	16.4

2.2.6 SEISMIC INTERPRETATION

2.2.7 WELL CORRELATION

Two wells were used for correlation because it contains the necessary log curves. Correlation result from the study area revealed a variation in the reservoir thickness of a particular well to the other. Magnitude of a particular formation property is usually measured by logging tools put into effect by a logging truck lowers the downhole instruments into the wellbore (Schlumberger, 2009). The logging data derived from logging are used to correlate zones across wells and support in hydrocarbon evaluation such as structures and isopach mapping, determine depths and thickness of hydrocarbon bearing zones, distinguish between hydrocarbon fluids in reservoir and evaluate hydrocarbon reserves of the zones of interest. The two wells with required log curves (GR, deep resistivity/LLD, neutron/NPHI, density/RHOB and sonic logs) were displayed side by side on the well section window in the petrel interface. The scales of each log were set. The GR log is commonly the first log on the first track. Shale cut-off was determined on a bimodal plot. GR record ranges between 0 and 150, the minimum value for the deep resistivity logs is 0.2 and a maximum value of 2000 on linear log scale. The neutron and density were combined together on the third track by reversing the NPHI. The scale used for the density log is 1.65 and 2.65 for the minimum and maximum values respectively. The minimum value for the neutron log was 0 and 60 for the maximum value. The wells placement on the well section was arranged on closest neighbours with the help of the information on the base map and cross section with Alamu well 5 as the first, followed by well 4 as viewed in figure 21. The sand bodies for all the wells were picked and correlated starting from the deepest well with the GR long motifs and shale thickness. The reservoirs were determined using the deep resistivity, neutron-density and acoustic logs. The

sand zones which contained oil were discriminated from those that contained gas with the neutron-density combined logs.

Fig 21: Well correlation spectrum

4.3.2 FAULT INTERPRETATION

Twelve different faults (F1–F12) were identified and mapped across the seismic data. The prominent faulting styles include growth faults with associated rollover anticlinal structures. The faults have a north-west south-east orientation as well as a north-east–south-west direction. Observations from a seismic arbitrary line A–A’ indicate that most of the faults have affected all the storage units (Fig. 22). It was also observed that the faults that are deeper have higher throws

than the shallower faults (Fig. 23). The variance time slice reveals that the faults are curved (listric) and the faults are better interpreted on the seismic in-lines.

Fig 22: Seismic section showing interpreted fault

Fig 23: Seismic section showing interpreted fault (Deep and shallow faults)

1.1.3 SEISMIC TO WELL TIE

Check-shot data for only one well (Alamu -4) was provided for this study as and this was shared among other wells. Only two wells (4 & 5) with necessary data such as density and sonic logs were used in generating synthetic seismograms as a way of initiating the seismic to well tie. First, a sonic data calibration with respect to available Check-shot was employed as quality control (QC) method for data consistency and check for invalid velocity information. It was

observed that velocity information followed expected trends, no abnormal velocity variation. Then a reflectivity co-efficient log was generated and convolved with a synthetic wavelet, this produce synthetic seismogram for each well. The seismogram was later compared with a set of traces around the wellbore and degree of correlation examined. No bulk time shift was applied in any of the wells to avoid distorting the velocity information as validated from the initial Check-shot data. A sample of the sonic data calibration, synthetic seismogram generation and seismic-well tie process for two well are shown in Figure 24 – 27

Seismic to well tie process for ALAMU 1, 2, 3 and 6 wells were skipped as they do not have the sonic log which is necessary for synthetic seismogram lie as shown in (Table II). For wells without Check-shot information, Check-shot data from nearby well was shared to place the wells within the time domain only. No seismic to well tie process was carried out for such wells.

Fig 24: Sonic Log to Check-shot Data Calibration for Alamu 5 Well

Fig 25: Synthetic Seismogram Generation and Seismic to Well Tie Process Panel for Alamu 5 well

Fig 26: Sonic Log to Check-shot Data Calibration for Alamu 4 Well

Fig 27: Synthetic Seismogram Generation and Seismic to Well Tie Process Panel for Alamu 4 well

1.1.4 STRUCTURAL AND FAULT FRAMEWORK OF THE ALAMU FIELD

Mapped horizons and the generated fault polygons were used to generate time structural maps for the 2 reservoirs. The time structure maps of the two horizons generated are shown in Figures 28. The contoured map has contour interval of 125 ms and the values range from -2500 ms (orange/yellow) to -2875 ms (purple/blue). Points of equal time are identified by same colour. In figure 28, the target area of hydrocarbon is the closure formed in the hanging wall closures by synthetic faults dipping in the northeast– southwest (NE–SW) direction.

The faults interpreted (Fig. 23) describe a complex structural setting with two major fault compartments (F1 and F12) or fault blocks that have been penetrated by the wells in the Alamu’s field.

Fig 28: Time structural map made from the interpreted horizons

CHAPTER FIVE

5.1

CONCLUSIONS

3-D structural analysis and well log data have been used to characterize the hydrocarbon-bearing sand bodies within the subsurface in the Alamu's field of Niger Delta, Nigeria. The study provided an insight into the structural architecture of the field via horizon and fault interpretation which help in generating time structural maps for two horizons. These maps revealed the structural geometry of the subsurface and the presence of possible trapping mechanism which controlled the accumulation in the Alamu's field. The fault interpreted describes the structural setting of the field which showed two major faults and some synthetic faults. The two major growth faults trend east–west (E–W) and dip south, and they define the regionally extensive structures with rollover. The structural plots of the tops of the reservoirs revealed that the hydrocarbon structures are fault-assisted anticlinal structures; and they match the peak/crest of the rollover anticlines on the seismic slices.

Petrophysical parameters were estimated and used in the determination of reservoir properties such as porosity, water saturation, hydrocarbon thickness, net-to-gross ratio, reservoir thickness and appropriate fluid contacts. Cross-plots constructed (neutron–density) to display the reservoir lithology. These cross-plots well log analysis reflect that the lithology from shaley sandstone to sandstone. The hydrocarbon zones were proven by petrophysical analyses that show high porosity, low water saturation, low shale volume, and high net–to–gross ratio.

5.2

RECOMMENDATION

In essence, the results of this study make a substantial contribution to our understanding of the underlying geology of the study region, it shows that to get the best out of every field and make correct judgments about hydrocarbon development. It is essential that proper analysis which involves components of this study are needed to be carried out effectively. The knowledge gleaned from this study can be a useful starting point for future exploration projects and resource estimation in the energy industry.

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